

The Effect of Capsaicin on Tomato Seed Germination

Introduction and Literature Review

The overuse of chemical fertilizers and pesticides have caused irreversible damage to the climate. To ensure continued growth and bolster production, many crops are treated with these harmful chemicals that can cause downstream effects on both human and ecosystem health. We want to study if there is a more natural alternative to these methods. Studying the effect of growth mediums on germination is important because seedling quality is affected by climate and growing conditions, which ultimately affects the yield of a crop produced (Arin and Arabaci, 2019). Climate change and erosion has led to decreased soil quality, which threatens food availability by limiting the amount of crops that can be produced (Garbowski et al., 2023). Climate change is also reducing the amount of available water to support vast agricultural lands (Garbowski et al., 2023). Agricultural lands are also being contaminated with heavy metals, such as lead and mercury (Garbowski et al., 2023). These consequences indicate that a natural alternative to these harmful chemicals must be found. The use of natural soil treatments also has many benefits, such as lowering soil salinity, maintaining soil pH, and reducing the movement of heavy metals in soil and to bodies of water (Garbowski et al., 2023).

Some research on how natural soil treatments affect seed germination has already been done. Mineral-based soil treatments allow for immobilization of heavy metals and reduces the ability of toxic materials to be extracted from soil (Garbowski et al., 2023). The use of organic soil treatments allows for increased carbon storage in the soil and reduced soil erosion, which leads to greater food safety for human populations (Garbowski et al., 2023). Regarding these organic treatments, Garbowski et al. (2023) found that sugarcane filtrate increased seed germination, plant height, and dry yield of lentil plants. Another mixture of composted livestock manure, humic acid and press muds applied on sorghum plants resulted in improved germination, dry yield, and nutrient uptake (Garbowski et al., 2023).

Known for its various culinary uses, it is no stretch to say that *Solanum lycopersicum*, or the tomato plant, is a worldwide dietary staple. The process of *S. lycopersicum* seed germination is well understood, with research projects focused on the various factors that control germination

rate and plant growth rate. One knowledge gap that exists is the effect of capsaicin on germination and plant growth rates of *S. lycopersicum*. Capsaicin is the major pungent component of *Capsicum* spp., more commonly known as the pepper plant (Ishikawa et al., 1998). The mechanism underlying the abundance and production of capsaicin across several pepper strains is genetically determined and varies between species (Aza-González et al., 2011). While an abundance of studies exist that cover the effects of capsaicin on human health and on its physiological role in other plant species, information about its impact on seed germination in *S. lycopersicum* is limited (Arin & Arabaci, 2019). Existing studies on capsaicin and seed germination currently do not assess a clear relationship between these two variables and disagree or differ across their findings (Kato-Noguchi & Tanaka, 2003; Barchenger & Bosland, 2016; Siddiqui & Arif-Uz-Zaman, 2005). The use of capsaicin as a growth medium could give home gardeners and the agricultural industry the opportunity to increase the growth of their crops without harming the consumer.

Considering that capsaicin is an allelopathic compound, it serves to protect planted seeds from competition with other invasive weeds by directly decreasing their presence (Tesio & Ferrero, 2010). Moreover, capsaicin has antifungal properties that prevent the germination of fungus hence protecting growing seedlings from mold allowing increased growth (Kraikruan et al., 2008; Arin & Arabaci, 2019). By investigating the relationship between capsaicin and seed germination for agricultural produce like tomatoes, we might potentially obtain a solution that can bolster the success rate of sprouting boosting crop production. Tomato seedlings encounter life-threatening challenges in their early developmental stages and are most susceptible to diseases such as damping-off and root rot, both of which are caused by fungi presence (Zhang et al., 2022). Global warming further contributes to the increased abundance of these fungi in agricultural crops because large temperature changes paired with high moisture levels create favorable conditions for fungi to grow and reproduce at an accelerated rate (Zhang et al., 2022). As a result, the increasing threat of fungi could lead to low tomato seed germination rates, crop depletion, and higher expenses incurred from treatments such as fungicides.

Wood ash was chosen as a comparative treatment for this experiment because it is known to carry several nutrients necessary for plant development. It also exists in excess in our current industrial environment, which necessitates the study of its effects on crops such as tomatoes. In particular, wood, sawdust, and rice bran ash are known to contain macronutrients necessary for

plant growth, such as nitrogen, potassium, and magnesium (Okon et al., 2024). It has also been shown that fruit weight and production of tomato plants has been improved when wood ash is applied to soil (Okon et al., 2024). Additionally, it has been found that wood ash significantly increased the nutrient content of vegetables (Okon et al., 2024). Another study completed by Arshad et al. (2020) also sought to determine the effects of wood ash on vegetable plant growth. In this study, it was found that neem wood ash increased the rate of germination and plant shoot growth of mung beans (Arshad et al., 2024). This indicates the benefits of wood ash application.

Our study will be conducted at the University of California, Los Angeles, at the La Kretz Botany Building. We will be studying the tomato plant, or *S. lycopersicum*, as well as capsaicin in the form of 100% cayenne powder and wood ash provided by the Ecology and Evolutionary Biology (EEB) department at UCLA, to determine the effects of capsaicin on seed germination in *S. lycopersicum*. We hypothesize that applying capsaicin, in the form of a solution containing 100% cayenne powder and distilled water, as a soil treatment will increase germination success in *S. lycopersicum* seeds compared to wood ash and untreated soil because capsaicin has antifungal properties. We predict that the frequency of sprouted seeds will be higher in capsaicin-treated soil than in wood ash-treated or non-treated soil.

Methods

Experimental Procedures

The study was conducted at La Kretz Botany Building at UCLA. For this study, the null hypothesis is that capsaicin-treated soil will have no statistically significant effect on seed germination in comparison to wood ash-treated or non-treated soil. The alternative hypothesis for this experiment is that capsaicin-treated soil will increase seed germination in a statistically significant way as opposed to wood ash-treated or non-treated soil. To test these hypotheses, the study design included three separate trays of 36 compartments, for a total of 108 compartments. Each tray contained a different group being studied, and individual compartments had two tomato seeds planted. Therefore, each group had 35 replicates, and the study had a total of 36 control samples. We used planter's soil, wood ash, and capsaicin in the form of organic cayenne powder with a purity of 100% cayenne (Simply Organic Cayenne Pepper). For watering purposes, we also used graduated cylinders and pipettes.

In this experiment, three drip trays containing 36 cells each were prepared as a control or receive one of two treatments (capsaicin solution, wood ash). We separated the treatment groups in order to avoid cross-contaminating the samples. We began by labeling one tray as ‘control’, ‘capsaicin’, and ‘wood ash’, respectively. We weighed eight grams of planter’s soil and carefully transferred it into each cell, gently packing the soil. We visually measured the soil for the remaining 35 cells to ensure they appeared to have equal amounts of soil and were gently packed. This was repeated for all trays, in the same steps outlined above. Using a popsicle stick marked at 0.5 cm, we measured out a depth of 0.5 cm below the surface of the soil and planted two tomato seeds per compartment at this depth. This was repeated for all trays and compartments. In all three drip trays and cells containing the tomato seeds and planter’s soil, we added one mL of distilled water to each compartment (a total of 36 mL of water per tray) a hour before applying the capsaicin treatment. This was done to equalize soil moisture across all cells. While doing this, we made sure it did not overflow or disturb the resting position of the previously planted seeds. This process was repeated for all compartments on all trays and the trays were put aside to rest until the concentrated solutions were prepared.

For the two percent w/v solution of cayenne powder that was applied as a soil treatment, we first prepared it by weighing 2.16 grams of organic cayenne powder (100% ground cayenne pepper) on an analytical balance. We chose a 2% w/v solution because seedlings are particularly sensitive to various environmental factors and did not want to compromise the survival of the seedlings by applying a higher than necessary concentration. As a result, we chose an intermediate concentration that is strong enough to observe its impact on germination. With a graduated cylinder, we measured 108 mL of distilled water. Next, we transferred the powder and water into a beaker and thoroughly stirred the mixture with a stirring stick for two minutes. We let it sit covered for 15 minutes to allow maximum capsaicin leakage into the water. We then prepared a funnel, lined with laboratory grade filter paper over a beaker, and gently stirred the solution, before straining it. We used a three mL micropipette, to measure three mL of capsaicin solution and gently administer it to a compartment. We repeated this step until all 36 compartments were treated with the solution for the tray labeled “Capsaicin”. We aimed to have uniform application of the capsaicin treatment in each compartment and have each compartment absorb about three mL of capsaicin solution ($3 \text{ mL} \times 36 = 108 \text{ mL}$). We only did a one-time application of capsaicin in this experiment because we are merely observing its impact on

germination, which is a short process that lasts around five to ten days. Subsequent waterings were completed with distilled water.

For the wood ash application, it was conducted similarly to the application of capsaicin. We used a five percent concentration solution. This concentration was chosen for our study because Okon et al. (2024) found that a five percent concentration produced the best germination rate out of the six concentrations they tested. To make this solution, we measured 5.4 grams of wood ash using an analytical balance. With a graduated cylinder, we measured 108 ml of distilled water and combined it with the wood ash. This mixture was thoroughly stirred for two minutes and filtered using filter paper. Using a pipette, three mL of the solution was applied to each of the 36 plant cells in the tray labeled “Wood ash.” We only applied this treatment one time and distilled water was used afterwards to water the seedlings for the same reasons we only applied capsaicin once.

In order to ensure each of the seeds are subject to the same rearing conditions, we needed to control for other variables such as the amount of light, water, and temperature. Each of the three prepared trays were subjected to a daily 12-hour light/12-hour dark cycle, provided through the use of a grow light. To water the seeds, we applied one mL of distilled water to each cell through a pipette, and repeated this process until we applied a total of three mL per cell. This process was repeated for all cells across the three trays and done daily throughout the germination process to ensure that the topsoil remains moist. We did not apply all three mL at once to each cell to avoid water logging the seeds. If the topsoil appeared moist, we only applied one mL for that day.

Statistical Analysis

The dependent variable for this study is the number of germinated seeds and the independent variable is the soil treatment type used. The data to be collected for the number of successfully germinated seeds is interval (number of sprouted seeds), and the data for treatment type is categorical (wood ash-treated soil, capsaicin-treated soil, non-treated soil). Samples had 35 replicates per treatment condition, and to ensure that samples were independent and unbiased each tray and their respective treatments were prepared separately. All samples had the same amount of soil, were given the same amount of water on the same schedule, and were kept under stable temperature and lighting conditions.

The data that we will collect during this experiment will be tracked using a shared Google Sheet, and statistical analysis will be done using the XLMiner Analysis Toolpak extension for Google Chrome. Since our study includes an independent categorical data variable and a dependent interval data variable, we will be using a Single Factor Anova Test through the XLMiner program for statistical testing purposes. Further, we will be running a two-tailed T test assuming equal variances between our capsaicin and wood ash groups to determine whether or not there is a significant statistical difference between their respective percent seed germination.

Results

After running our data through the Single Factor Anova test, we found that the number of groups in our study was three, with each group having a corresponding count of 36. The average percent seed germination was 25% for the control, 4.16% for the wood ash, and 30.55% for the capsaicin (see Figure 1). For this test, the P-value result we collected was the between groups P-value because our hypothesis stipulates that capsaicin will outperform the other treatment types in seed germination success. The between group P-value of this experiment was 0.0002 which is less than the significance level of 0.05. However, because the wood-ash percent seed germination was unexpectedly low, we performed a post hoc two-tailed T-test between the capsaicin and control group, finding a two-tailed P value of 0.3066 which exceeded the 0.05 significance level.

Figure 1: Average Percent Seed Germination vs. Treatment Types. Bars represent average percent of seeds germinated per treatment type, error bars represent uncertainty around these averages.

Discussion

Our between-group Anova P-value of 0.0002 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in seed germination between the three groups (control, capsaicin, and wood ash). However, when we furthered our analysis with a post hoc two-tailed T-test on capsaicin and control group, we found a P-value of 0.1533, which indicates that seed germination between these two groups was not statistically significant. We performed a two-tailed T-test because the results of our experiment were unexpected. As a result, we fail to reject the null hypothesis which asserts there is no statistically significant difference between the treatment groups and the control in relation to seed germination. Our hypothesis was not supported.

We felt that the amount of replicates that we had was sufficient because there were plenty of samples in the event that some did not germinate. In the future, we think we might decrease the concentration of wood ash, as 5% w/v may have been too high of a concentration for the sensitive seedlings to handle. Based on our previous literature review, this concentration of

wood-ash should have increased germination success rates in comparison to the control. We may have used too high of a concentration or the lack of a precise analytical balance may have led to an overestimation of the amount of added wood-ash to the treatment solution. Accuracy when creating the wood-ash solution is crucial because too high of a concentration can increase soil pH, which negatively affects the seedlings nutrient uptake (Bang-Andreasen et al., 2017). We also attempted to utilize a bottom watering method to encourage uniform capillary uptake across the cells for the first two days, which left the plants much drier than expected. This could explain the slow germination rate, as our seeds took 11 days to start germinating instead of the expected eight to ten days. Although, it is possible that it occurred within the expected time frame and we just happened to miss it over the weekend.

Although the specific concentration of capsaicin we used did not significantly improve seed germination rates, in comparison to the control, it does add to our knowledge of natural soil treatments and their potential effects on climate change. It is possible that capsaicin is not an effective soil treatment for increased seed germination as presumed, or that this concentration and the manner in which it was applied was not effective. Despite the root cause, it can be assumed that capsaicin is not among the most suitable treatments to improve seed germination. Previously, it was mentioned that organic soil treatments have the ability to reduce erosion and increase soil carbon storage, helping offset the effects of climate change (Garbowski et al., 2023). It is also known that carbon storage increases as organic treatment use increases, which could lead us in the direction of future research (Aguilera et al., 2013). Capsaicin, being an organic molecule, could have had the ability to help reduce the amount of harmful chemicals used on our agricultural crops, and reduce climate change in the process. Interestingly, another study found that aqueous extracts of red pepper containing capsaicin significantly inhibited germination and seedling growth in wheat, reinforcing the idea that plant-derived compounds can act as strong allelochemicals, depending on the species of plant and stipulated concentration (Iqbal, et al., 2015). This aligns with our inconclusive results and suggests that further research should explore varying doses, application techniques, and species dynamics in relation to allelochemicals to optimize and further explore the agricultural use of capsaicin.

References

- Aguilera, E., Lassaletta, L., Gattinger, A., Gimeno B. S. (2013). Managing soil carbon for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Mediterranean cropping systems: A meta-analysis, *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, (168), 25-36.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2013.02.003>
- Arin, L., & Arabaci, C. (2019). The influence of exogenous capsaicin application on the germination, seedling growth, and yield of pepper. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 43(5), 500–507. <https://doi.org/10.3906/tar-1903-86>
- Arshad, S., Iqbal, M., Shafiq, M., Kabir, M., & Farooqui, Z.-U.-R. (2020). *The effects of wood ash on seed germination and seedling growth of pulse crop Vigna radiata (L.) R. Wilczek.* <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejfood.2020.2.1.21>
- Aza-González, C., Núñez-Palenius, H. G., & Ochoa-Alejo, N. (2011). Molecular biology of capsaicinoid biosynthesis in chili pepper (*Capsicum* spp.). *Plant cell reports*, 30(5), 695–706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00299-010-0968-8>
- Bang-Andreasen, T., Nielsen, J. T., Voriskova, J., Heise, J., Rønn, R., Kjøller, R., Hansen, H. C. B., & Jacobsen, C. S. (2017). Wood Ash Induced pH Changes Strongly Affect Soil Bacterial Numbers and Community Composition. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 8, 1400. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01400>
- Barchenger, D. W., & Bosland, P. W. (2016). Exogenous applications of capsaicin inhibits seed germination of *Capsicum annuum*. *SCIENTIA HORTICULTURAE*, 203, 29–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2016.03.009>
- Garbowski, T., Bar-Michalczyk, D., Charazińska, S., Grabowska-Polanowska, B., Kowalczyk, A., & Lochyński, P. (2023). An overview of natural soil amendments in agriculture. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 225, 105462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2022.105462>

- Ishikawa K., Janos T., Sakamoto S., & Nunomura O. (1998). The content of capsaicinoids and their phenolic intermediates in the various tissues of the plants of *Capsicum annum* L. *Capsicum and Eggplant News* 17, 22-25.
https://cpi.nmsu.edu/_assets/documents/cap17.pdf
- Iqbal, M. Z., Ahmend, L., Shafiq, & Athar, M. (2015). Allelopathic effects of red pepper (*Capsicum annum* L.) and coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) on early seedling growth of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Advances in environmental research*, 4(1), 1-15.
<https://doi.org/10.12989/aer.2015.4.1.001>
- Kato-Noguchi, H., & Tanaka, Y. (2003). Effects of Capsaicin on Plant Growth. *Biologia Plantarum*, 46(1), 157–159. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1027317906839>
- Kraikruan, W., Sangchote, S., & Sukprakarn, S. (2008). Effect of capsaicin on germination of *Colletotrichum capsici* conidia. *Kasetsart Journal: Natural Science*, 42, 417–422.
- Okon, S. L., Sunday, A. E., Umoh, F. O., & Ekwere, O. J. (2024). Influence of Wood Ash Concentration on Coastal Plain Soil, Growth and Yield of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) in a Humid Tropical Zone of South Eastern Nigeria.
- Siddiqui, Z. S., & Arif-Uz-Zaman. (2005). Effects of *Capsicum* leachates on germination, seedling growth and chlorophyll accumulation in *Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek seedlings. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 37(4), 941–947.
[https://www.pakbs.org/pjbot/abstracts/37\(4\)/20.html](https://www.pakbs.org/pjbot/abstracts/37(4)/20.html)
- Tesio, F., & Ferrero, A. (2010). Allelopathy: A chance for sustainable weed management. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 17(5), 377–389.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2010.507402>

Wani, L. B., Gama, P. B. S., Marcelo-d'Ragga, P. W., & Misaka, B. C. (2015). Effect of soil media on growth of tomato seedlings (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) under nursery (greenhouse) conditions. *International Journal of Agricultural Research and Review*, 3(10), 1–9. <https://www.springjournals.net/articles/166421102015>

Zhang, Y., Li, Y., Liang, S., Zheng, W., Chen, X., Liu, J., & Wang, A. (2022). Study on the Preparation and Effect of Tomato Seedling Disease Biocontrol Compound Seed-Coating Agent. *Life (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12(6), 849. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life12060849>

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank our lab instructor Veronika Vucaj and the teaching staff of EEB 100L for their guidance and support with this experiment. We would also like to extend our gratitude to the Ecology and Evolutionary Biology Department at UCLA for providing us with the opportunity, materials, and space needed to complete the experiment.